

The Influence of Cultural Values, Tourist Motivation, and Word Of Mouth towards the Destination Image and the Implications of Visit Intention (Study on Tourist Destinations in Yogyakarta)

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Abstract: Yogyakarta is the second largest tourist destination after Bali and is one of the tourism destinations in Indonesia, which is important because of its appeal. Unfortunately, Yogyakarta only ranks far away from expectations as areas that obtains the title as a tourism city. Overall, there was indeed an increase in the number of foreign tourists visiting Yogyakarta through Adi Sucipto Airport from 2012 until 2014, but the growth rate decreased drastically. This study aims to analyze the tourist visiting behavior patterns by using variables of tourists' cultural values, tourists' motivation to visit, word of mouth as an independent variable, destination image as an intervening variable, and tourists' intentions to visit as a dependent variable. The method used in this research is qualitative descriptive and causality methods. The samples taken were 350 tourists visiting five (5) major tourist destinations in Yogyakarta. The research result showed that cultural values influenced the image of destination, yet did not influence the tourists' intention to visit. Meanwhile, the motivation to visit did not influence the destination image but influenced on the intention to visit. Word of mouth variable influenced the destination image and the intentions to visit. Destination image mediated the influence of cultural values and word of mouth to the tourists' intentions to visit, but did not mediate the influence of motivation to the tourists' intentions to visit.

Keywords: Foreign tourists cultural values, motivation to visit, word of mouth, destination image, intention to visit, tourism marketing

PREFACE

According to The World Travel & Tourism Council (WTTC), Indonesia has the most excellent growth in tourism among other G20 countries. WTTC estimated Indonesia had the opportunity to achieve growth in foreign tourists by 14.2 percent and domestic tourists by 6.3 percent in 2014. The contribution of the tourism sector to the economy was expected to reach 8. 1 percent. This was evidenced by the increased number of foreign tourists visiting Indonesia up to December 2014.

The followings are data of foreign tourists’ visits on 19 main entrances:

Table 1.1. Foreign tourists visits based on entrance, 2012 – 2014

No.	Entrance	2012		2013		2014	
		Visit	Rank	Visit	Rank	Visit	Rank
1	Soekarno Hatta	2,053,850	2	2,240,502	2	2,246,437	2
2	Ngurah Rai	2,902,125	1	3,241,889	1	3,731,735	1
3	Kulanamu/Polonia	205,845	5	225,550	5	234,724	5
4	Batam	1,129,608	3	1,336,430	3	1,454,110	3
5	Sam Ratulangi	19,111	16	19,917	16	17,279	16
6	Juanda	197,776	6	225,041	6	217,193	6
7	Entikong	25,897	13	24,856	15	22,464	15
8	Adi Sumarmo	21,612	14	17,738	17	12,911	19
9	Minangkabau	32,768	12	44,135	12	50,196	13
10	Tanjung Priok	66,168	10	65,227	11	64,941	12
11	Tanjung Pinang	103,785	9	99,593	9	97,672	9
12	Bandara Inter.Lombok (BIL)	17,032	17	40,380	13	69,881	11
13	Makasar	13,881	19	17,730	18	15,713	17
14	Sepinggan	16,828	18	16,904	19	13,156	18
15	Sultan Syarif Kasim II	21,387	15	25,946	14	27,382	14
16	Adi Sucipto	58,926	11	86,02	10	89,156	10
17	Husein Sastranegara	146,736	7	176,318	7	180,392	7
18	Tanjung Utan	336,547	4	318,154	4	320,861	4
19	Tanjung Balai Karimun	107,499	8	104,889	8	100,782	8

Source: Statistics Indonesia (2014)

Data in Table 1.1 shows that Bali is the major tourism destination in Indonesia. As the major tourist destination, Bali is expected to keep improving its quality as a tourist destination to lift the other areas that have similar characteristics in Indonesia. Indonesia's tourism excellence which has become the most prominent in the Cultural and historical heritage tours and natural beauty (The Travel and Tourism Competitiveness Index 2013) encourages regions of Indonesia which mostly have cultural heritage, and natural beauty to be well-developed. The competitive advantage that has successfully developed tourism in Bali is apparently still not fully able to raise promote other tourist areas outside Bali. Tourist destinations in Yogyakarta (DIY), for examples, which was declared the second tourist destination in Indonesia ranked 10th in 2012, 9th in 2013, and 11th in 2014 in terms of foreign tourists visits (Statistics Indonesia, 2014).

Special Region of Yogyakarta (DIY) is a province-level autonomous region in Indonesia with the province capital is in Yogyakarta, a city with a range of predicates, both from history and the existing potentials, such as the city of struggles, the city of culture, city of students, and tourism city. Yogyakarta as a tourism city illustrates the potential of this province in tourism point of view. Yogyakarta is a popular second largest tourist destination after Bali and is one of the tourism destinations in Indonesia, which is quite important because the appeals it offers. Firstly, Yogyakarta has rich ancient sites, such as Prambanan, Kota Gede, Taman Sari, Ratu Boko, the Palace, and the temples scattered around the region, this wealth of ancient sites can serve as a mainstay in Yogyakarta tourism. Secondly, Yogyakarta has a typical folk crafts, especially batik and pottery with competitive quality with other regions. Third, Yogyakarta has the power of culture, particularly the very strong Javanese culture inherent in the citizens' life. And fourth, Yogyakarta has the potential of interesting nature tourism such as Parangtritis, Hutan Bunder, as well as beaches located in Gunung Kidul like Baron, Samas, Krakal, Kukup, and Drini. With such excellences, Yogyakarta has a chance to become one of destinations in culture tourism, historical heritage, and natural richness and beauty.

In fact, based on the data in Table 1.1. Yogyakarta was ranked very far from expectations as areas that received the title as a tourism city. There were indeed an increase in the number of foreign tourists visiting the province through Adi Sucipto Airport from 2012 until 2014, but the growth rate had decreased drastically.

For further analysis, researchers conducted a preliminary survey on 40 tourists visiting several destinations in the province. The survey showed that the majority of foreign tourists stated that their cultural values are perceived differently by the Yogyakarta cultural values. Cultural values inherent in a tourist will certainly affect their perceptions of a destination. Cultural values influence the patterns of travel and information search of a tourist destination (Litvin, Crofts and Hefner, 2004). Culture offered by the service provider will collaborate with foreign tourists' cultures and affect the tourist visiting behavior (Litvin, Crofts and Heiner, 2004).

Another important thing to observe is the study on the foreign tourists' motivation. A foreign tourist motivation to visit, in any form, is intended to get contributions in accordance with what has been sacrificed (money, time and work) to fulfill the needs when traveling. Managing motivation is the recognition and provision of the needs of travelers in the offerings in the tourism industry to be achieved. The preliminary study result showed from 40 sampled foreign tourists, mostly were motivated for reasons of Curiosity and Culture, Relaxation and Pleasure. To fulfill the tourist demands, there needs to be a strong tourism destination imaging in Yogyakarta in terms of cultural aspect, which raises the tourists' curiosity. Foreign tourists' destination imaging should be directed to the image of the suitability of destination image with foreign tourists' motivation to visit, so the tourists will be satisfied with the destination they visit as it's in line with their expectations.

In addition, another important component to be explored is the promotion of tourist destination image. The promotion of a tourist destination image is an activity that introduces a tourism area to potential visitors to make them visit or wish to visit again. The activity must be sustainable for it's a part of the communication tools in marketing. One component of the communication activities that has the most noticeable effect is the retelling the uniqueness of a tourist destination to another, or often referred to as the Word of Mouth (WOM). The question is, how a story/history/communication done by a company is obtained and matched its compliance by foreign tourists. However, the preliminary study result in Table 1.2 shows that 21 or 52.5% of foreign tourists feel they didn't get enough information about tourist destinations in Yogyakarta before visiting. This indicates that the information provided through marketing activities has yet

to fulfill the tourists' needs about tourist destinations in Yogyakarta. To investigate more about the acquisition of information, researchers then asked foreign tourists about tourist destinations resources they receive.

One important factor is the correspondence between the tourism destinations offered with the image promoted to visitors (Bui, 2011). Congruent destinations would greatly affect the development of tourism in a tourist destinations (Bui, 2011). Thus, an analysis on the tourist destination image in Yogyakarta is needed. Preliminary study result showed that foreign tourists felt tourist destinations in Yogyakarta didn't match their expectations, so the researchers felt the need to observe in more depth about the suitability of destination image promoted by travel service providers with foreign tourist motivation to visit.

This study is an approach to consumer behavior which has always been a subject of interest (Yoon & Uysal, 2005). On the other hand, Backman and Crompton in Huh (2006) uses an attitude approach based on the preference or intention to visit. This study undertakes a review of a number of important variables to consider in the development of a destination and its compliance with foreign tourist perception as a consumer of a tourist destination.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The concept of tourism marketing was first defined by Krippendorf (1971), stating that: "Marketing in tourism as a systematic and coordinated execution of business policy by tourist undertaking whether private or state owned at local, regional, national or international level, to achieve the optimum satisfaction of the needs of identifiable consumer groups and in doing to achieve an appropriate return." This definition was used by Yoeti (2005) as follows: Tourism marketing is a system and coordination that should be done as a discretion for tourism industry group companies, either private or state-owned, within the scope of local, regional, national or international in order to achieve tourists' satisfaction by obtaining a reasonable profit.

Further understanding of tourism marketing was also formulated by other authors that stated tourism marketing is a management process which is carried out by national organizations or enterprises including those in the tourism industry group to identify tourists who already had desires to travel and those who have the potential to travel by way of communicating with them, influencing the desires, needs, motivating to what they like or not, at local, regional, national or international levels, by providing tourists objects and attractions in a bid obtain tourists' optimum satisfaction (Yoeti, 2005).

Culture and Cultural Values

The definition of culture covers a vast range of meaning. In 1952, Kroeber and Kluckhohn compiled a list of 164 definitions of culture. As the conclusion of an extensive analysis, they suggested a comprehensive definition of culture: "Culture consists of explicit and implicit patterns, and behavior acquired and transmitted by symbols, which is a distinctive achievement of human groups, including the embodiment of the artifacts. The essential core of culture consists of traditional ideas (i.e. historically derived and selected) and especially the values engraved in a cultural system that on the one hand is regarded as a product of action, and on the other hand as an element conditioning further action "

Cultural values are base concepts that includes elements such as values, beliefs and norms that collectively distinguish certain groups of people from others (Pizam, 1997). Wide shared values programmed into the individual in subtle ways from an early age (Otaki., 1986), are resistant to change (Hofstede, 1991) and remain clear when at home or while traveling abroad (Pizam and Reichel, 1996; Pizam and Sussmann 1995).

Schwartz (1994) defined the cultural values as socially desirable concepts used to represent these goals mentally and the vocabulary used to express them in social interaction. That definition is consistent with the definition suggested by Kluckhohn (1951) that cultural values as a generalized and organized conception, Influencing behavior, or nature, of man's place in it, of man's relation to man, and of the desirable and non desirable as they may relate to man-environment and inter-human relations and Rokeach (1973) who stated that value as an enduring belief that a specific mode of conduct or end-state is personally preferable to its opposite. Based on the three definitions, the cultural values can be defined as a general concept that is socially organized and used to express social interaction in inter-human relationship and human - environment relationship.

Individual values reflect the unique experience of the individual (individual values), as well as the influence of normative culture (cultural values), so that these values can be analyzed on individual and culture levels (Schwartz, 1994). On the individual level, a number of value priorities reveals the trade-offs of an individual to pursue a certain value. This means that an individual emphasizes the important values, while discourages less important or opposing values. Using the smallest two-dimensional space analysis, Schwartz (1994) believed that the level of an individual is arranged along two basic dimensions, the so-called conservation to be open to change and the self-transcendence for self-improvement. In both dimensions, ten individual dimensions are identified representing possible conflicts and compatibility between the values. The types of individual values are described as follow (Schwartz and Bardi, 2001): Power; Achievement; Hedonism; Stimulation; Self-direction; Universalism; Virtue; Tradition; Suitability.

Travel Motivation

Pizam, Neuman, and Reichel in Plangmarn (2012) stated that travel motivation refers to a set of needs that cause a person to participate in a tourist activity. The motivation is also defined as the need that drives an individual to act in a certain way to achieve the desired satisfaction (Beerli and Marti'n, 2004). While Fodness (1994) in Plangmarn (2013) stated that motivation theories describe a dynamic process of internal psychological factors (needs, desires and goals) which generate a level of tension in an individual and influence him or her towards purchase. It can be concluded that the motivation to visit is a series of needs that makes a person willing to participate in a tourist activity and attempt to get the desired satisfaction.

Referring to Crompton (1979), most tourist motivations are related to tourist destinations selection decisions that are based on Push and Pull factors. Tourists are pushed and pulled by some sources from various forces. These forces explain how the individual is driven by internal variables, and how they are driven by a tourist destination (Uysal & Hagan in Plangmarn, 2013). Push Motivation is a socio-psychological motivation or internal motivation coming from human's tangible or intrinsic desire which includes motivation: Pleasure; Relaxatio: rest and recreation, Health; Participation in sports; Curiosity and culture; Ethnic and family; Spiritual and Religious; Status and prestige; Professional or business.

On the other hand, Pull Motivation is a motivation that arise due to tourist destinations instead of from the tourists themselves. Pull factor includes tangible and intangible components from a specific destination that attracts people to realize their need for the tourist experience, such as: natural and culture attractions, food, local residents, recreational facilities, and destination image being marketed. Push Motivation is used to explain the desire to go traveling, while the Pull Motivation is used to choice the destination.

Word of Mouth

Word of Mouth is defined as oral, person-to-person communication between a receiver and a communicator whom the receiver perceives as non-commercial, regarding a brand, product or service (Brit, 1966; Arndt, 1967; Bayus, 1985; Bolting, 1989). Consumers often reckon "WOM as more credible and trustworthy, comparable to others, and social networks usually accept WOM more willingly (Liu, 2006; Banerjee, 1993; Brown and Reingen, 1987; Murray, 1991). It can be concluded that the Word of Mouth (WOM) is the informal communication between the two reliable parties, which is comparable and socially acceptable, regarding the evaluation of goods and services.

This definition prompted many researchers to measure WOM in terms of the frequency and the number of people who receive it (eg. Bowman and Naryandas, 2001; Eliashberg, Jonker, and Sawhney, 2000; Godes and Mayzlin, 2004; Liu, 2006). However, this approach failed to address the power and scope of WOM. In addition, several studies revealed the characteristics of message, including the rational and emotional dimension of message Allsop, Basset and Hoskins, 2007; Mason and Davis, 2007) and the importance of words, content, body language and expressions in WOM message (Hogg, 2000). The WOM message content details and delivery seems to offer an alternative conceptualization of WOM. This communication approach for WOM is unique, given the previous concept was to focus on volume and valence.

Actually Godes and Mayzlin (2004) noted the importance of WOM content, but didn't address this issue in their studies. Furthermore, Eliashberg et al. (2000) also admitted that WOM measuring is not a

matter of black and white when they describe their simplifying assumptions, but it is considered necessary to address the effectiveness of WOM message in the context of low-involvement products. Old literature reviews, including Aristotle discussions, suggested three types of communication characteristics: 1. Favorableness or valence; 2. Emotional aspects that reflect emotion or enthusiasm; 3. Cognitive aspects related to the details of WOM (Harrison-Walker, 2001; Mazarol, Sweeney and Soutar, 2007).

Destination Image

Lawson and Bovy (1977) defined the concept of destination image as the expression of all objective knowledge, prejudices, imagination and emotional thoughts of an individual or group about a particular location. On the other hand, another researcher defined destination image as the sum of all beliefs, ideas and impressions that people associate with a destination (Crompton, 1979; Kotler, Haider and Rein, 1993), while Bigne, Sánchez and Sánchez (2001) defined destination image as the subjective interpretation of reality by the tourist. In parallel with the previous definition, San Martín and Rodríguez (2008) stated that the image tourists have of a destination is largely subjective because it is based on the perceptions each tourist has of all of the destinations they have been to or have heard of. It can be inferred that destination image is exceedingly subjective because it is based on the perception of each tourist regarding a destination they have visited or heard.

According to Ecthner & Brent Ritchie (2014), there are three components of destination image as follow:

1. Functional Characteristics Attribute

Functional physical attributes that related to a tourism destination, comprising: (a) condition of tourism destination, (b) condition of total parking area, (c) climate, and (d) condition of infrastructure

2. Functional and Psychological – Holistic Characteristics

Functional, psychological and holistic physical attributes that related to a tourism destination, comprising: (a) personal security, (b) tourism development, (c) reputation, (d) impression

3. Psychological Characteristics Attribute

Psychological characteristics attributes that related to a tourism destination, including: (a) citizens' hospitality and (b) environmental sustainability.

Visit Intention

Woodside and Lysonski (1989) stated that visit intention is the perceived likelihood that a tourist will visit a particular destination within a specific time period. According to their model, visit intention is a consequence of two exogenous factors, namely foreign tourist characteristics and marketing activity influence.

Intention becomes the main predictor in determining behavior, because it is created. Such thing is in line with Schiffman and Kanuk's statement (2010) which stated that intention as the thing related to one's tendency to perform particular actions or behaviors. Corsini (2002) in The Dictionary of Psychology defined intention as a decision to certain behavior. In addition, Ajzen (2005) stated that intension could be explained through the planned behavior theory, a further development of the reasoned action theory. Intention reflects individual willingness to try certain behavior.

In another reference, Ajzen (2005) mentioned that intention is indicator used to measure someone's beliefs on attempting certain behavior as well as his/her efforts to do so. Intension is correlated with behavior. Therefore, it can be used to predict behavior. Ajzen's basic paradigm (1985, 1991) on intention is well-known as Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) which elaborated that individual will tend to perform particular behavior if: (1) the behavior has valuable results, (2) the important parties respect and approve the behavior and (3) they have the resource, ability and opportunity needed to conduct those behaviors (Lam and Hsu, 2006). Specifically, attitude, subjective norm, and behavior control influence behavior intention.

TPB is originated from the assumption that individuals could behave wisely, so they calculated the existing information, either implicitly or explicitly and considered the impact of their behavior. Such theory stated that individual's intention to show or to hide a certain behavior is the most determining factor of behavior occurrence. In addition, Ajzen (2005) mentioned that intention is divided into three aspects, comprising: attitude toward the behavior, subjective norm perceived behavior control

METHOD

According to Hair et al. (2007), the total sample is minimum 5 times of total parameter used in the research. Since the parameters or indicators in this research are 67 points, so the samples used here are 335 foreign tourists. In order to prevent any possibilities, researcher distributed questionnaires to 380 foreign tourists.

Non-probability with quota sampling is chosen as the sampling technique in this research which is conducted by determining the certain number as the target that must be achieved in the sample collection from the population (particularly the unlimited and the unclear ones). With the certain target, the researcher then collect the sample randomly until fulfilling the sample required. In this research, foreign tourists (as the samples) are divided proportionally according to the planned tourism destination area, including Prambanan Temple, Yogyakarta Palace, Purawisata, Gembira Loka, as well as Taman Sari. There are 70 foreign tourists in each tourism destination, so the total sample is 350 foreign tourists.

RESEARCH RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This section aims at describing analysis unit condition based on research variables. In order to show the more comprehensive illustration about analysis unit, the description of responses filled out by the respondent is created. The result of this research showed that foreign tourist respondents are those who love the activities due to hedonist reasons. Other reasons are because they also require stimulant or encouragement to do activities and they believe that human beings are basically equal (universalism), willing to hold good values in life, required to improve their prosperity and to maintain the indigenous culture and tradition in daily life.

On the travel motivation variable, natural, cultural, culinary attractions, and people's hospitality became the motivation to encourage foreign tourists to visit Yogyakarta. It indicates that most of foreign tourists are motivated to come to tourism destination in Yogyakarta because of its natural beauty, unique traditional culture, local culinary and the hospitality of local people. In addition, the result of the research also indicated that the vast majority of foreign tourists have positive and negative impressions, have obtained information about tourism destination and to do list in Yogyakarta in details, and have got references about the must visit tourism destinations from others.

Data analysis result showed that destination image is positive. This indicates the vast majority of respondents consider tourism destinations in Yogyakarta are well developed, have good reputations and good impressions for them. On the other hand, the analysis for visit intention variable showed that foreign tourists are willing to visit Yogyakarta because they got good experiences at their first visit or because they heard interesting stories from other people about tourism destinations in Yogyakarta. Other reasons are because they have enough resources to travel and they choose Yogyakarta as the main tourism destination to visit if they have the opportunity to travel.

At this stage, the result of measurement model estimation for each construct is comprehensively retested to seek the level of match between the first measurement model and the research data. According to RMSEA, Normed Fit Index (NFI), Non-Normed Fit Index (NNFI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI), Incremental Fit Index (IFI), and Relative Fit Index (RFI) statistics, the result of measurement model testing is in the *Good Fit* level. Whereas, based on the Goodness of Fit Index (GFI) and Adjusted Goodness of Fit Index (AGFI), the result is in the Marginal Fit level. Marginal fit is approaching to fit (Bentler, 1990 in Wijanto, 2008: 58). Meanwhile, CMIN/DF measurement model is 2,41 or included in Good Fit category. Therefore, it can be concluded that the model fits the data and is able to capture the correlation between the investigated phenomena.

The analysis is then continued by research hypothesis testing. The result of hypothesis testing indicated that cultural values and word of mouth partially has a positive and significant influence on destination image, while the travel motivation has no significant influence on destination image.

This is in line with the research conducted by Litvin, Crofts and Hefner (2004) which found out that cultural values play a significant role in affecting traveling pattern and information seeking of a tourism destination which is eventually influence the perception on destination image. The similar research result is also found on the study done by Sizoo, Steve, Eileen Kupper and Jerome Agrusa (2011) which stated that cultural sensitivity influences the tourism destination image of a country and eventually influences its tourism destination image.

Moreover, the research result also showed that foreign tourists obtained positive and negative information (Word of Mouth) for other people who have visited tourism destination in Yogyakarta. Kotler & Keller (2007) elaborated that Word of Mouth Communication (WOM) is a communication process in giving recommendation, either individual or group, about a product or service in order to convey information personally. Word of mouth communication is one of the popular communication channels used by the companies, both goods and service, due to its effectiveness to ease the marketing process and its ability to give benefits to the companies. According to Kotler & Keller (2007), word of mouth personal communication channel might be an effective promotion method because it is delivered from one consumer to another. So, it could be a good advertisement channel for companies if customers are satisfied.

The result of hypothesis testing showed that visit motivation partially has a significant influence on word of mouth. The influence of visit motivation and word of mouth on visit intention is positive, while the cultural values motivation of foreign tourists has no significant influence on visit intention, indicated by the zero hypotheses.

The research result for cultural values is in line with result of the research conducted by Plangmarn, Acheraporn, Mujtaba, Bahaudin G, Pirani, Mohamed (2012) which stated that cultural values of foreign tourists influence their perception on destination image. However, it has no influence on their intention to visit a particular tourism destination. The research result is possible because the visit intention of foreign tourist to tourism destination in Yogyakarta is based on their perception about the destination acquired from the seeking information process by using mass media or other particular resources. The visit intention of foreign tourist is not based on their cultural values or its compatibility to cultural values in Yogyakarta. Therefore, the compatibility of foreign tourists' cultural values and the destinations' cultural values needs no review.

On the motivation variable, this research is parallel with result study conducted by Plangmarn, Acheraporn, Mujtaba, Bahaudin G, Pirani, Mohamed (2012) which confirmed the research result if Yan, Wu (2013). Both previous researches stated that foreign tourists' visit motivation has a significant influence of visit intention to tourism destination. When examined more deeply, there are basic things need to be considered by the tourism destination management to increase the motivation of foreign tourists in visiting tourism destinations in Yogyakarta. As previously explained, the motivation of foreign tourists to visit tourism destinations in Yogyakarta is based on external factors or the tourism destination factor itself.

On the word of mouth variable, the result is in line with research conducted by Yan, Wu (2013) which stated that the word of mouth received before the visit of foreign tourists influence the visit intention to the tourism destinations. Based on the previous discussion, it has been explained that the most important story for foreign tourists about tourism destination in Yogyakarta is from the point of view of "positive message" indicator. It means foreign tourists consider visiting tourism destination in Yogyakarta because of the positive message delivered by word of mouth from other people. It needs to be focused especially on the formulation of tourism programs and services development plan in Yogyakarta.

Based on the results of data analysis, it is known that the destination image variable significantly influences the visit intention of foreign tourist. This is in parallel with research conducted by some researchers, including Greaves, Nicola and Skinner, Heather (2010), Parng, Benjamin.C, Mu-Ken Chen, and Tsung-Thing Ching (2014), and Mohammad M and Ab Ghani NI (2014). Those three previous research results showed that the destination image has a significant influence on the visit intention of foreign tourists. It means if the destination image is positive, the foreign tourists will be willing to visit tourism destinations in Yogyakarta. These results strengthen the evidence of how important the positive tourist destination image to increase the number and frequency of foreign tourists visit to tourism destinations in Yogyakarta.

To test the role of mediation in destination image variable, the mediation testing is conducted by using Baron and Kenny's formula (1986). The calculation result showed that the destination image partially mediates the influence of cultural values on visit intention of foreign tourists or the occurrence of partial intervening. Furthermore, destination image also partially mediates the influence of word of mouth on visit intention of foreign tourist or the occurrence of partial intervening. Destination image is not an intervening variable for the indirect influence of motivation on foreign tourists' visit intention. It can be concluded that destination image is an exogenous variable in this research model.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

In cultural values variable, most foreign tourists who were respondents in the study liked the activity for hedonist reasons, requiring a stimulant or an urge to perform the activity, arguing that human beings are basically the same and equal (universalism), willing to defend the values of goodness in life, arguing that one should increase the prosperity in life, and always accepting and retaining the original cultural traditions in everyday life.

In the motivation to visit variable, most of the foreign tourists were motivated to visit Yogyakarta tourist destinations for its natural beauty, unique traditional culture, distinctive culinary and hospitality of the locals. Thus, the majority of foreign tourists might not initially think to go to travel to a certain destination, but because of getting information about the natural beauty, cultural tourism, culinary tourism, and the hospitality of the locals, tourists would decide to travel to tourist destinations in Yogyakarta.

In Word of Mouth variable, most tourists had ever get both positive and negative impressions, ever received attractive and detailed information about tourist destinations in Yogyakarta, received information about things to do while visiting tourist destinations in Yogyakarta, and got reference of which tourist destinations that should be visited from other parties. In tourist destination image variable, most tourists positively portrayed tourist destinations in Yogyakarta in the sense that tourist destinations in Yogyakarta are sufficiently developed, have good reputation and create a pleasant impression for tourists. In the intention to visit variable, most respondents stated that the intention has been high. This means that tourists are willing or interested in visiting Yogyakarta because they got a good first time visit experience, or they obtained interesting experiences stories from other parties regarding the tourist destinations in Yogyakarta, as they have sufficient resources for a visit, and will make Yogyakarta as a main tourist destination to be visited in case they want to travel and have the opportunity to travel.

In tourist destinations image variable, there was a positive and significant effect to the intention to visit. That means, if the destination's image is positive, the tourists will be willing to visit tourist destinations in Yogyakarta.

The findings in this study indicates that the word of mouth becomes a dominant factor in the establishment of strategies for improving the destination image and the foreign tourists' intention to visit. This means that the understanding of the information flow process that occurs among foreign tourists becomes essential to improve the tourist destination image and intention to visit. Advanced research in the future should be directed in examining aspects of word of mouth received by foreign tourists before and after the visit to cultural tourist destinations, in broader scale, in order to present the word of mouth in general. This needs to be done to enrich the development of science, especially the science of marketing associated with increased foreign tourists' intention to visit in the tourism industry.

Another interesting study on the same topic also needs to be directed in a larger scale, for example a national scale that also includes maritime destination in the island of Sumatra, Kalimantan, Eastern Indonesia which use different cultural approaches. Thus, a comparison can be done in terms of cultural values, motivation to visit and word of mouth between the various tourist destinations. The findings of the study are quite valuable for the contribution to the development of the marketing science in the tourism industry in Indonesia.

Some important things to enhance foreign tourists' intentions to visit through the understanding of cultural values, motivation to visit and word of mouth are as follow:

1. Designing cultural art programs that display characteristic of Yogyakarta cultures, for example: Yogyakarta typical dance, Yogyakarta typical food, Yogyakarta traditional transportation, Yogyakarta typical food availability at hotels and lodges in Yogyakarta.
2. Designing a sport tour or tour program in Yogyakarta like surfing or diving, etc.
3. Providing Yogyakarta typical food/culinary at lodges in Yogyakarta.
4. Adding tourism promotion program on destinations in Yogyakarta to foreign countries.
5. Packing information interestingly about the uniqueness of Yogyakarta tourism and tourist destinations to abroad through the available media information.
6. Adding or expanding the parking lot at each destination in Yogyakarta
7. Maintaining and repairing buildings/infrastructures that become the icon of tourist destination in Yogyakarta.
8. Improving tourist services provided by the tourist destinations to gain foreign tourists good impressions about Yogyakarta.

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